

On-Demand HAPS-Assisted Communication System for Public Safety in Emergency and Disaster Response

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Abstract—Natural disasters often disrupt communication networks and severely hamper emergency response and disaster management. Existing solutions, such as portable communication units and cloud-based network architectures, have improved disaster resilience but fall short if both the Radio Access Network (RAN) and backhaul infrastructure become inoperable. To address these challenges, we propose a demand-driven communication system supported by High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS) to restore communication in an affected area and enable effective disaster relief. The proposed emergency response network is a promising solution as it provides a rapidly deployable, resilient communications infrastructure. The proposed HAPS-based communication can play a crucial role not only in ensuring connectivity for mobile users but also in restoring backhaul connections when terrestrial networks fail. As a bridge between the disaster management center and the affected areas, it can facilitate the exchange of information in real time, collect data from the affected regions, and relay crucial updates to emergency responders. Enhancing situational awareness, coordination between relief agencies, and ensuring efficient resource allocation can significantly strengthen disaster response capabilities. In this paper, simulations show that HAPS with hybrid optical/THz links boosts backhaul capacity and resilience, even in harsh conditions. HAPS-enabled RAN in S- and Ka-bands ensures reliable communication for first responders and disaster-affected populations. This paper also explores the integration of HAPS into emergency communication frameworks and standards, as it has the potential to improve network resilience and support effective disaster management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters, such as earthquakes, hurricanes, floods, and wildfires, have long demonstrated their catastrophic impact on communities worldwide. These events often cause massive loss of life, destruction of property, and extensive disruption to essential infrastructure, particularly communication networks. For example, the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami devastated coastal regions

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in Southeast Asia, claiming over 230,000 lives and displacing millions. Similarly, the 2010 earthquake in Haiti left more than 160,000 people dead and led to widespread devastation, exposing significant weaknesses in the country's communication systems. In the United States, Hurricane Katrina in 2005 caused severe damage to New Orleans, disrupting communication networks and hindering emergency response efforts. These events have all underscored the vulnerability of existing communication infrastructures in times of disaster, making it clear that effective communication systems are critical for timely response and recovery. The recent earthquakes in Türkiye in February 2023 are a stark reminder of these challenges. With magnitudes of 7.7 and 7.6, these earthquakes devastated entire cities in southern Türkiye, claiming over 50,000 lives and displacing millions of people. The destruction of critical infrastructure, especially communication networks, made it difficult for rescue teams and survivors to make contact immediately after the disaster. The collapse of ground-based communication systems severely hampered rescue efforts, delayed coordination, and exacerbated the crisis, highlighting the urgent need for more resilient and rapidly deployable communication solutions in disaster scenarios [1].

In response to these challenges, technical solutions have been developed to improve communication in emergencies. Public safety agencies around the world are increasingly focused on ensuring that communications systems remain operational during disasters. In the United States, for example, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) has introduced the Mandatory Disaster Response Initiative (MDRI) to improve the resilience of wireless networks. This initiative includes measures such as bilateral roaming agreements and mutual aid between service providers to reduce network outages and speed up recovery. Portable communication systems such as Cells on Wheels (COWs) have also been deployed in Australia to ensure connectivity in areas affected by bushfires and flooding. These systems are rapidly deployed in disaster areas to maintain communication between emergency responders and the affected population when traditional infrastructure is damaged. The authors in [2] propose a resilient, multi-layered network architecture that integrates the existing infrastructure with new layers, including cloud processing. The new architecture aims to improve the scalability and resilience of communication networks in the event of a disaster. Cloud computing is integrated to provide flexible and scalable Information and Communication Technology (ICT) services and reduce dependency on physical infrastructure. Geo-redundancy and load-balancing techniques are also implemented to manage

Figure 1. Illustration of the proposed on-demand HAPS-assisted private network.

network traffic and ensure high availability. In [2], two new optimal integer linear program models are proposed that exploit the intrinsic interplay between data and service evacuations and can efficiently use the early warning time before cloud data centers are affected.

However, while these solutions help to a degree, they still have limitations, particularly in the face of widespread disasters that render existing communication infrastructures unusable. Following the 2023 Türkiye earthquakes, for instance, large swathes of the affected regions were without power for extended periods, further complicating efforts to restore telecommunications. These challenges highlight the need for even more innovative and adaptable solutions to bridge communication gaps in such critical times.

One potential solution is the use of High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS) [3]. In disaster scenarios, it is studied for different aims like improving access link or backhaul link [1], [4] or providing aerial computing services for the terrestrial Internet of Things (IoT) devices [5]. Operating in the stratosphere, HAPS offer several advantages that make them suitable for disaster response. Their ability to cover vast areas, rapid deployment, and minimal reliance on ground-based infrastructure make them a powerful tool for providing on-demand communication in disaster-stricken regions. HAPS can establish reliable communication channels quickly, ensuring that emergency responders and affected populations can communicate with each other and coordinate relief efforts. This can significantly enhance situational awareness, improve coordination between agencies, and facilitate more efficient resource allocation, ultimately saving lives and reducing the impact of the disaster. This paper explores the potential of a HAPS-assisted communication system tailored specifically for public safety during emergency and disaster response. By addressing the communication gaps exposed during past disasters, including the Türkiye earthquakes, HAPS could play a crucial role in enhancing the resilience of disaster management frameworks, ensuring that timely and effective responses are possible even in the most challenging conditions.

II. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The proposed private on-demand network consists of a central station, intermediate HAPS nodes, and an end-point HAPS node, as shown in Fig. 1. It has its isolated backhaul through HAPS nodes using FSO links and HAPS-assisted Radio Access Network (RAN) that operates on both existing cellular frequencies and Ka-band. The central station must be located in a secure region, as it is responsible for controlling and deploying the private network when necessary. This central station acts as a disaster management and control center, integrating high computing capacity for efficient operations. The control station should be centrally located (e.g., in the geographical center of the country) to minimize the distance to disaster-affected areas. It includes a ground station for communication with the first HAPS intermediate node. All collected data is processed at this central station to facilitate disaster response through various management and planning strategies, which will be detailed in the following sections. Although the proposed on-demand private network is primarily for public safety, it also has gateways to connect commercial communication networks that can serve as a parallel core network to support communication in the disaster area. In addition to the technical advantages, locating a disaster management center in a region that is not affected by the disaster also has psychological advantages (e.g., it is common practice to appoint a temporary governor or decision-making staff in the affected areas to prevent people from acting emotionally in such cases). The central station can also include energy technology enablers such as Photovoltaic (PV) panels, battery storage systems, and diesel generators to ensure power continuity.

The proposed on-demand emergency network has intermediate HAPS nodes that are responsible for backhaul communication between the ground station and the affected region. Depending on the distance to the ground station, several nodes may be required. These HAPS nodes can be designed to fly independently or be transported as cargo to other locations. Recent advances in the field of HAPS show that these nodes can be deployed and transferred to a certain

distance in just a few hours. These flying objects are equipped with solar panels to provide the energy needed to relay the communication load from the affected area to the central station and vice versa.

The end-point HAPS node in the proposed system serves multiple functions in restoring communication and collecting data in disaster-affected regions. It assists terrestrial Base Stations (BSs) in re-establishing (damaged) backhaul connections and provides backhaul or uplink communication for Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Some UAVs function as BSs when terrestrial infrastructure is disrupted, while others, equipped with sensors and cameras, support disaster assessment through real-time data collection. In addition, the end HAPS node itself can communicate with users on the ground if required. Finally, the end HAPS node may also carry some high-resolution cameras that can be used to capture footprints (in clear sky) from the region, just as we now use satellite imagery services for disaster management assessment and planning.

III. TECHNOLOGY ENABLER FOR PROPOSED SCENARIO: PRIVATE NETWORK

A. Over-the-Air Communication

Inter-HAPS Free-Space Optics (FSO) Communication: Backhaul:

Disaster assessment and management require a vast amount of data sharing between the first responders and the operation planning center. This data includes the collected images from the area, command communication for the rescue operation, and planning for first aid such as shelter, food, etc. These inter-HAPS backhaul links can be established with FSO communication from the ground station to the end-point HAPS node, as shown in Fig. 2. FSO communication has the capacity to replace fiber-optic wired backhaul links as long as a Line-of-Sight (LoS) link is secured. Since the HAPS nodes are operated nearly 20 km above the earth, a direct LoS can be guaranteed without any weather events (such as clouds, fog, or rain) since these events occur at much lower altitudes than the stratosphere.

Hybrid FSO/THz Communication: Fronthaul/Backhaul for Terrestrial BSs and UAVs: Terrestrial telecommunication infrastructure can be severely affected by disasters. In most cases, the terrestrial BS might be completely unavailable due to physical damage, power outage, etc. On the other hand, the fronthaul/backhaul links might be disrupted, although the BS itself can stay operational. The end-point HAPS node can assist terrestrial infrastructure in these scenarios. A backhaul link can be established from HAPS to operational terrestrial BSs through a hybrid FSO/Terahertz (THz) communication. Unlike inter-HAPS communication, THz communication may also be needed in this case since the FSO links can be affected by weather events, while THz has much more resiliency against these events. Therefore, a hybrid FSO/THz communication link seems an optimal solution, as shown in Fig. 2. However, as mentioned above, the terrestrial BS might be completely nonoperational. In this scenario, temporary (several) UAV-BS can be transferred to those regions to replace the terrestrial BSs. The established FSO/THz communication backhaul links to UAVs will be crucial to restore communication in these regions.

Figure 2. Disaster area communication network.

In addition to restoring communication, surveillance and data collection from the region have a crucial role in effective disaster response planning. In this context, UAVs equipped with cameras and sensors play a vital role in disaster assessment and rescue operations. However, collecting data from these high-resolution cameras and transferring them to the operation center has challenges when the network is already facing disruptions and congestion. Therefore, the hybrid FSO/THz communication from end-point HAPS to surveillance UAVs (as shown in Fig. 2) can guarantee uninterrupted data collection to have effective disaster response planning for authorities.

Direct Access to Ground Users: RAN: The end-point HAPS node is also capable of providing direct access to ground users. To eliminate the need for additional devices, direct communication with mobile handheld devices should be established in the S-band (the same frequencies with existing cellular networks) so they can connect to HAPS just as terrestrial BS. This capability plays a critical role in delivering essential information, such as shelter locations, first aid availability, and food distribution points, to affected populations across all regions. Since this service is expected to require low data rates, it can be effectively supported by the end-point HAPS. Meanwhile, uninterrupted communication between the coordination center and first responders is crucial for effective disaster management. Under current conditions, first responders typically communicate with the command center via push-to-talk radios or satellite links. However, these systems have several limitations, including limited range and service disruptions. To overcome these challenges, direct access from HAPS can ensure high-data-rate, uninterrupted communication, provided that first responder vehicles are equipped with Very Small Aperture Terminals (VSATs) in the Ka-band. The Radio Frequency (RF) communication strategy in both scenarios aligns with ITU's frequency allocations for HAPS as defined in [6].

B. The Role of Mobile Applications, AI and Data Processing in the Central Station

The data collected in the zone affected by the disaster can be analyzed in the central station, which is not affected by the disaster. While traditional data analytics can process and interpret this information, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques can provide a more advanced, adaptive and automated approach that enables a faster and more efficient response to disasters, especially in situations where predefined human-generated models are too rigid or cannot capture the complexity and unpredictability of disaster events. Therefore, AI techniques can play a critical role in reducing disaster risk by predicting extreme events and creating hazard maps, enabling real-time event detection and situational awareness, providing decision support for emergency responders, and automating emergency networks [7]. This improves root cause analysis, predictive maintenance, and network infrastructure optimization. AI algorithms can serve various purposes in disaster management. First, they optimize resource distribution by analyzing the needs of affected areas, predicting demand, and determining the most efficient delivery routes [8]. Second, they assess the impact of disasters by analyzing satellite imagery, drone footage, and other visual data to automatically evaluate damage. Third, AI can process vast amounts of data from social media to provide real-time insights that help locate survivors, identify urgent needs, and track the spread of both accurate information and misinformation during post-disaster recovery. On the other hand, virtualization and cloud computing can enable emergency services to process and analyze large amounts of data in real time. These technologies can offer flexibility, fast recovery, and better security through firewalls and microservices. Cloud-based architectures that support resilient and fault-tolerant emergency networks can ensure continuity during disasters.

Geographical Information Systems (GIS) can serve as effective tools for the visualization, analysis, and interpretation of disaster-related data and support all phases of disaster management [9]. First, GIS improves risk assessment and preparedness by identifying areas at risk through the analysis of geographic and demographic data. By evaluating factors such as population density, infrastructure distribution, and historical disaster trends, GIS enables better disaster planning and mitigation strategies. Second, GIS improves the situational awareness of disasters in real time by integrating data from multiple sources, including weather reports, satellite imagery and sensor networks. This dynamic mapping capability allows emergency responders to monitor unfolding events, predict affected areas, and adjust response strategies accordingly. Third, GIS plays a crucial role in optimizing resources and logistics by identifying effective paths and distribution centers. By analyzing transportation networks and accessibility constraints, GIS can aid disaster management teams in allocating resources effectively and ensure the timely delivery of emergency aid. Fourth, GIS facilitates evacuation planning and execution by designing optimal evacuation routes based on terrain analysis, road conditions, and population movement patterns. This helps authorities to implement safer and

more effective evacuation plans to reduce casualties and congestion during emergencies. Finally, GIS supports post-disaster recovery and public communication by mapping the affected areas, assessing the damage, and identifying the critical infrastructure that needs to be restored. In addition, GIS improves public awareness by presenting clear visualizations of risks, safety measures, and recovery efforts, helping communities make informed decisions in disaster situations.

Mobile applications serve as an effective tool for providing real-time updates, guiding evacuation routes, and delivering safety guidelines during earthquakes and recovery efforts. Over-the-Top (OTT) apps, including apps for voice and data communication, video distribution, and conferencing, are widely used by emergency services. Some apps are directly connected to the Public Switched Telephone Network for emergency calls. Many OTT apps rely on cloud-based solutions and virtualization to ensure scalability and security. These apps support session recording and multi-party connectivity, which is essential for public safety answering points. Mobile OTT applications can provide users with critical information, enabling them to make informed decisions and take necessary actions to stay safe during and after an earthquake. For instance, applications such as “MyShake” and “ShakeAlert” utilize smartphone sensors to detect earthquakes and issue early warnings upon detection. Beyond early alerts, these applications can also offer guidance on emergency procedures, evacuation paths, and a “Safe Corner” property to aid users identify the safest sheltering spots. Additionally, they provide comprehensive resources on earthquake preparedness, safety measures, and recovery efforts, along with interactive maps displaying the locations of nearby earthquake early warning sensors. Additionally, technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) can contribute to disaster preparedness by simulating crisis scenarios and providing hands-on training for emergency responders. These immersive tools enhance crisis management skills, improving real-world disaster response capabilities.

IV. CASE STUDY

In this section, we demonstrate the communication capabilities of the proposed on-demand HAPS network in a disaster-struck area. We show simulation results for each communication protocol discussed in the previous section. Overall simulation parameters for each setup are given in Table I.

To demonstrate the backhaul capabilities of HAPS networks in Fig. 1, we obtained the simulation results for the data rates achieved at the HAPS endpoint as shown in Fig. 3. This figure illustrates the data rates at the HAPS endpoint as a function of the distance between the central station and the region potentially affected by the disaster, taking into account a different number of intermediate HAPS nodes. In our simulations, the HAPS nodes are located at the first-point, intermediate-point, and end-point at an altitude of 20 km. Since there is no rain or clouds in the stratosphere under normal atmospheric conditions, we use FSO for data transmission between the central station and the end-point HAPS node. Additionally, the transmitter and receiver antenna gains, along with atmospheric

Table I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS USED IN EVALUATIONS FOR EACH SETUP.

FSO Link		THz Link		Ka-band Link		S-band Link	
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Laser wavelength	1550 nm	Frequency	144 GHz	Frequency	30 GHz	Frequency	2.4 GHz
Transmit power	17.5 dBm	Transmit power	17.5 dBm	Transmit power	43.2 dBm	Transmit power	43.2 dBm
Tx and Rx optical efficiencies	0.8	Signal bandwidth	30 GHz	Signal bandwidth	400 MHz	Signal bandwidth	100 MHz
Receiver telescope diameter	80 mm	Tx antenna gain	55 dBi	Tx antenna gain	13.8 dBi	Tx antenna gain	13.8 dBi
Tx and Rx pointing errors	1 μ rad	Rx antenna gain	55 dBi	Rx antenna gain	39.7 dBi	Rx antenna gain	0 dBi
Full transmitting divergence angle	15 μ rad	Noise spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz	Noise spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz	Noise spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz

Figure 3. End-to-end backhaul capacity for the proposed on-demand HAPS network by using FSO communication. The x-axis shows the bird's-eye distance of the disaster region to the central station, and the y-axis shows the achievable backhaul capacity with different intermediate HAPS nodes.

attenuations due to Mie scattering and geometrical scattering, are modeled as proposed in [10], while cloud, fog, and rain attenuations are based on [11]. The remaining communication parameters can be found in Table I. As expected, with more intermediate nodes, the backhaul capacity increases. Nevertheless, even in the worst-case scenario with 3 HAPS (including the end-point HAPS node) in total 800 km distance to the disaster area, 200 Gbps data can be transferred in both directions which is quite enough for a backhaul link. This amount can increase up to 450 Gbps in a shorter distance with more intermediate HAPS nodes.

The fronthaul/backhaul capabilities between the end-point HAPS and UAVs, mobile communication terminals, and ground BSs deployed in the disaster-affected region were investigated using hybrid FSO/THz communication links in Fig. 4. The performance comparisons are given for randomly distributed UAVs and mobile terminals in an area with a 50 km radius under different atmospheric conditions, including clear sky, clouds, fog, and rain. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the FSO link exhibits superior performance to the THz link under clear sky conditions. However, clouds and fog impose significant attenuation on the vertical FSO link, mainly due to Mie scattering. In contrast, the vertical THz link performs better in cloudy and foggy conditions. Regarding rain conditions, the THz link experiences severe degradation due to strong absorption and scattering of

Figure 4. Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the data rates achieved at the terrestrial BS and UAVs by hybrid FSO/THz fronthaul/backhaul links.

THz signals, which result from their resonant interaction with electromagnetic waves in this frequency range. Although the FSO link is also affected by heavy attenuation in rainy weather, it performs better than the THz link under such conditions. In summary, our simulation results indicate that a hybrid FSO/THz communication approach can provide reliable large-scale disaster area connectivity, effectively adapting to different atmospheric conditions.

In Fig. 5, the Radio Access Network (RAN) connection between the end-point HAPS and the users on the ground operates in both S-band and Ka-band. S-band supports mobile handheld devices, while Ka-band requires VSAT terminals (60 cm circular polarization), which can be permanently installed or mounted on mobile platforms such as vehicles (e.g. emergency responders) or UAVs. For S-band simulations, considering an urban scenario, 1 million users are randomly distributed within an area of 50 km radius and served by the end-point HAPS. In the Ka-band simulations, 1000 VSAT devices are randomly distributed within the same area and served. All simulations incorporate HAPS parameters, air-to-ground channel characteristics, and receiver specifications as referenced in [1]. The simulation results indicate that a single HAPS can replace failed ground BSs to cover all mobile users in the area. Even in the worst case, mobile users can achieve 250 Kbps data that enables them to receive emergency-related data. This can be broadcast information (e.g., shelter, first-aid, food locations) or precautions shared via mobile

Figure 5. CDF of data rate in direct access to ground users. In the S-band, ground users are mobile handheld devices while in the Ka-band ground receivers have VSAT.

applications, as discussed in detail in the previous section. As we can see from Fig. 5, direct access to the ground mobile users can increase up to 120 Mbps, and this proves the proposed on-demand HAPS network can even replace commercial communication beyond public safety. On the other hand, VSAT receiver antenna gain compensates for the higher pathloss in Ka-band and enhances Quality-of-Service (QoS). This allows uninterrupted high-rate communication for first responders as envisioned. Moreover, the Ka-band is less affected by atmospheric conditions compared to the FSO and THz bands, whereas the S-band remains more resilient under rainy and cloudy conditions.

V. STANDARDIZATION EFFORTS AND CURRENT INITIATIVES

In the previous section, we demonstrated that the proposed HAPS-assisted communication network can play a crucial role in disaster response efforts. However, integrating HAPS public safety communication requires adherence to specific international standards, frameworks, and protocols. These standards define how HAPS, or other Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) such as satellites and terrestrial networks work together to provide resilient, scalable, and low-latency emergency communication systems. This section provides an overview of key global standards and protocols that define the role of HAPS and NTN in public safety communication.

A. 3GPP Standardization for NTN and HAPS Integration

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) serves as the primary standardization body responsible for defining how NTN integrate with terrestrial Fifth Generation (5G) and beyond. The framework includes HAPS, Low Earth Orbit (LEO), Medium Earth Orbit (MEO), and Geostationary Orbit (GEO) satellites. A major advancement in this domain is 3GPP Release 17, which introduces NTN-specific enhancements to 5G networks. Key improvements include HAPS-to-ground and HAPS-to-satellite communication, NTN integration with 5G New Radio (5G NR), and support for Direct-to-Device (D2D) NTN communication. Building upon this foundation, 3GPP Release 18 expands NTN capabilities by incorporating AI-driven network optimization for public safety

applications, enhancing HAPS-satellite-terrestrial interoperability. The ongoing evolution of 3GPP standards will further refine the integration of HAPS into NTN architectures, ensuring seamless connectivity in emergency scenarios.

B. ITU-R Standards and Regulations for HAPS-Based Communication

The International Telecommunication Union Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) defines HAPS spectrum allocation, network interoperability, and disaster management in the Radio Regulations (RR). Operating at altitudes between 20-50 km, HAPS platforms provide fixed broadband access and emergency connectivity, especially in disaster-stricken and underserved regions. ITU-R F.1500 specifies technical characteristics and spectrum allocations for HAPS in the 47/48 GHz and 2 GHz bands, ensuring compatibility with terrestrial and satellite networks while minimizing interference. ITU studies estimate spectrum needs ranging from 396 MHz to 2,969 MHz for ground-to-HAPS links and 324 MHz to 1,505 MHz for HAPS-to-ground, covering broadband and disaster relief applications. At the ITU World Radiocommunication Conference 2023, HAPS was formally recognized as a High-Altitude IMT Base Station (HIBS), enabling aerial 5G broadband services. Spectrum identification in the 2 GHz and 2.6 GHz bands allows HAPS to deliver real-time emergency communication, network restoration, and mobile broadband expansion [6]. Continued ITU-R standardization will be key to ensuring HAPS scalability, resilience, and integration into future 5G and NTN ecosystems.

C. Efforts from Industry for HAPS-Based Communication

In addition to government and international regulatory efforts, industry-led standardization initiatives play a critical role in defining the operational framework for HAPS-enabled communications networks. The HAPS Alliance, a global consortium that includes SoftBank, Airbus, and Aerostar, is actively working to develop technical standards for air-to-ground, air-to-satellite, and inter-HAPS communications [12]. Research efforts within the alliance focus on optimizing HAPS network topology, spectrum management, and system interoperability to ensure that these platforms can be rapidly deployed for public safety and emergency response operations. One of the most significant real-world deployments of HAPS for public safety was Google's Loon project, which demonstrated the feasibility of HAPS-powered emergency communications during Hurricane Maria in Puerto Rico (2017). Following the disaster, Loon deployed its stratospheric balloons and restored mobile network connectivity to over 200,000 people in the affected region. This highlighted the role of HAPS-based emergency response and demonstrated the restoration of low-latency and high-reliability networks. Similarly, in Asia, Japanese telecommunications companies, including NTT, KDDI, SoftBank, and Rakuten Mobile, have collaborated on disaster response initiatives, conducting joint training exercises with marine vessels and shared refueling stations to ensure rapid network restoration during large-scale natural disasters [13].

D. Space Agency Initiatives for HAPS-NTN Public Safety

Various national space agencies and research institutions are also contributing to developing HAPS-based NTN public safety networks. In the United States, NASA is leading efforts in HAPS-NTN emergency communications in collaboration with NOAA, FEMA, and the U.S. Department of Defense. The NASA HAPS-NTN Emergency Communications Study examines the role of stratospheric communication platforms for wildfire, hurricane, and earthquake response. This research includes AI-driven predictive modeling and optimizing the placement of HAPS networks for disaster scenarios. The Strategic Tactical Radio and Tactical Overwatch (STRATO) Project by NASA explores LTE-based HAPS connectivity for emergency responders, enhancing situational awareness in remote fire-prone regions [14]. The European Space Agency (ESA) is leading the SAT-HAPS Convergence Initiative, integrating HAPS and satellite-based emergency communication networks into European disaster management frameworks. This initiative aims to strengthen multi-layered NTN architectures, ensuring continuous public safety communication even in disaster-affected zones [15].

E. Future Directions in HAPS and NTN Public Safety Standards

As the role of HAPS in public safety communications continues to grow, future standardization efforts will focus on the full integration of HAPS into next-generation NTN architectures. This includes refining the HAPS to 5G NTN protocols in 3GPP Release 18 and beyond, extending ITU-R frequency allocations to support global HAPS deployment, and developing AI-driven network optimization models to improve real-time emergency communications performance. In addition, the emergence of multi-layer HAPS satellite-terrestrial architectures will improve the resilience and efficiency of emergency communications networks. The combination of HAPS, LEO, MEO, and GEO satellite constellations will enable seamless connectivity in disaster-prone, remote, and underserved regions, ensuring that first responders and affected populations have access to reliable communication channels during emergencies.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Reliable communication is essential for effective disaster relief, but traditional infrastructures often fail in large-scale crises. While solutions like cloud-based systems and portable units offer some resilience, they remain limited when both radio access and backhaul networks are disrupted. This paper has explored the potential of HAPS as a transformative solution for disaster communications. In contrast to conventional systems, HAPS can reestablish backhaul connections in addition to offering mobile users on-demand access, guaranteeing smooth communication between disaster management centers and impacted areas. By acting as an aerial bridge, HAPS facilitates real-time data collection from disaster-affected regions, provides critical information to emergency responders, and improves situational awareness for better coordination of relief efforts. The simulation results show that integrating HAPS with hybrid FSO/THz communication links enables the achievement of sufficient backhaul

capacity and network resilience, even under adverse atmospheric conditions. In addition, HAPS-enabled RAN connectivity in S- and Ka-band ensures robust communications for first responders and the affected population, which can be adapted to various disaster scenarios. Overall, HAPS-assisted networks offer a promising pathway toward a more resilient and adaptive emergency communication framework. Future research should prioritize optimizing deployment strategies, enhancing energy efficiency, and integrating AI for dynamic network management. By harnessing these advancements, HAPS can play a pivotal role in minimizing communication disruptions and enhancing disaster response effectiveness, ultimately saving lives and reducing the overall impact of disasters.

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